

A Brief History of Gaseous Dielectrics Research at NIST

J. K. Olthoff and L. G. Christophorou
National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, USA

Abstract: Researchers at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) have investigated gaseous dielectrics for more than 20 years. Significant technical accomplishments in this area include a detailed understanding of the physics and chemistry of corona-induced decomposition of SF₆, the determination of important collisional cross sections for dielectric gases, the development of conditional detection techniques for partial discharges, and assessment of potential replacement gases for SF₆. These and other research areas will be highlighted in this brief history of gaseous dielectrics research at NIST.

Introduction

The use of gaseous dielectric materials has promoted the development and application of compact high voltage equipment. The desirable properties of a gaseous dielectric for use in high voltage applications are rather straightforward [1], and include a high dielectric strength, relative ease of use, safety, and moderate price. Sulfur hexafluoride (SF₆) was recognized early on as having many of these properties, and therefore was adopted by the electrical equipment industry as their dielectric gas of choice.

However, the effective application of SF₆ to high voltage equipment and full acceptance of its use as a dielectric required significant research related to the behaviour of SF₆ under varied electrically stressed conditions. NIST, among other research institutions, responded to this need, and performed much of the research that was the basis for the reliable, safe, and common use of SF₆ today.

Gaseous dielectrics research began at NIST around 1980 with work that focused on partial discharge inception in SF₆ and various gas mixtures containing SF₆. Discharge inception behavior was investigated for both positive and negative corona as a function of pressure, electrode conditions, and optical irradiation [2,3]. It was shown that photodetachment, collisional detachment, and negative ion densities can influence discharge inception. This triggered an interest in the chemistry of discharges that occur in SF₆-containing gases, which lead to the significant NIST work on the decomposition of SF₆ in corona discharges, along with other research projects related to gaseous dielectrics.

In this paper, we will briefly review some of the significant accomplishments of the NIST gaseous dielectrics program over the past two decades. Obviously, there was related work being performed at institutions outside of NIST, however, the brevity of this paper forces us to concentrate almost exclusively on the contributions made by NIST researchers.

Corona-Induced Dissociation

Sulfur hexafluoride has a high recombination rate for reforming itself after it is dissociated in a discharge. This is one of the characteristics that makes it an excellent gaseous dielectric, especially for use in circuit breakers. However, in the presence of impurities, such as water and oxygen, some fast and complex chemistry occurs with the fragments of SF₆ that produces a plethora of byproducts. Some of these byproducts are toxic and/or corrosive. An understanding of the formation processes of these byproducts was necessary in order to understand the impact of their formation on SF₆-insulated equipment.

In 1985, Dr. Richard Van Brunt of NIST published a definitive article on the production rates of oxyfluorides commonly formed in corona discharges occurring in SF₆-containing gases [4]. This work presented results of the most comprehensive study of absolute yields of oxyfluorides from SF₆ corona in the presence of small quantities of O₂ and H₂O.

The experimental system consisted of a clean, 3.7 liter, brass discharge cell that contained a stainless steel, point-plane electrode assembly. The corona discharge was maintained at constant current, and the byproducts were detected using a gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer (GC-MS) system. The large volume of the discharge cell and correspondingly small concentrations of byproducts reduced the effects of secondary reactions, thus allowing the determination of primary production rates.

The results of this research showed that SOF₂, SO₂F₂, and SOF₄ are the dominant byproducts produced by corona in SF₆-containing gases. It also showed that for concentrations of O₂ or H₂O above about 1%, the rate limiting factor for byproduct production was the dissociation rate of SF₆, not the amount of impurity. Several gas-phase mechanisms were proposed to explain the observed dependence of the byproduct production rates on time and discharge current.

Figure 1: Measured absolute charge rates of production of by-products formed in negative point-plane glow corona produced in SF_6/N_2 mixtures [1,6].

In an effort to validate these proposed mechanisms, an intensive effort to model the decomposition of SF_6 and the subsequent formation of byproducts in corona was undertaken. The proposed chemical model consisted of three zones, and was composed of more than 80 relevant chemical reactions [5]. The model yielded dependencies of stable neutral oxidation byproducts as a function of time, discharge current, and O_2 and H_2O concentrations that were consistent with the measurements. However, the model was unable to reproduce absolute production rates, due in part to the large number of reactions for which rates or cross sections were unknown. The effort to obtain such data by NIST researchers is discussed in the next section.

Early interest in utilizing mixtures of SF_6 with other gases as dielectrics then led to research of decomposition products formed by corona discharges in mixtures with N_2 [1,6]. Figure 1 shows results from that investigation as a function N_2 concentration. Increasing N_2 concentration was observed to reduce most absolute byproducts production rates, which may be a benefit in industrial applications of these mixtures. The significant increase in SO_2 production rate with increasing N_2 is of particular interest, indicating the

potential of using SO_2 production for corona detection in dilute $\text{SF}_6\text{-N}_2$ mixtures.

In the early 1990s, there was considerable concern by the electric power industry over the possible production in commercial SF_6 -insulated equipment of S_2F_{10} , a highly toxic byproduct of electrical discharges in SF_6 . The concern originated from the fact that a threshold limit value for exposure to S_2F_{10} was set at 0.01 ppm [7], and no method existed for detecting S_2F_{10} at that level in the presence of SF_6 . NIST, in collaboration with other labs, then developed a GC-MS method that had a detection limit sufficient to meet this requirement [8]. Further research that utilized this method indicated that S_2F_{10} did not pose a significant safety issue to the electric utilities using SF_6 insulated equipment.

Fundamental Processes in SF_6

The complex chemical mechanisms proposed to explain the production rates of oxyfluoride byproducts in corona discharges in SF_6 [4], and the lack of large blocks of data in the SF_6 decomposition chemical model [5], clearly indicated the need to measure cross sections and rate coefficients for critical processes. NIST performed many such measurements over the years in collaboration with many other institutions.

One example of such a measurement was the determination of reaction rates of SOF_2 and SOF_4 with water [9] that were performed in collaboration with Oak Ridge National Laboratory. Another example was the determination of rate constants for F^- transfer from SF_6^- to fluorinated gases, such as those formed by corona discharges [10]. Both of these experiments provided data necessary for the validation of proposed mechanisms of byproduct formation.

NIST also worked in collaboration with the College of William and Mary to make the first measurements of collisional electron detachment and collision-induced dissociation cross sections for binary collisions of SF_6^- , SF_5^- , and F^- with SF_6 and rare gases [11]. These measurements clarified the role of negative ions in discharge inception in SF_6 by showing that the thresholds for collisional electron detachment from SF_6^- and SF_5^- are high (near 90 eV). This implies that discharge initiation by collisional detachment involves primarily F^- or negative ions formed from impurities.

More recently, a complete sets of electron-interaction cross sections and electron transport coefficients for SF_6 have been derived at NIST from the best experimental data [12]. These data sets were determined by a consistent analysis of the available experimental data that were then supplemented by new measurements where needed.

Figure 2: NIST recommended cross section set for electron interactions with SF₆. Definitions of symbols can be found in [12].

The assessed set of electron-interaction cross section data for SF₆ is shown in Figure 2. These data were developed primarily in response to the needs of the semiconductor industry for fundamental data used in their plasma modeling codes.

Partial Discharge Detection and Analysis

Partial discharge (PD) phenomena have long been of interest because they often occur at defect sites in electrical insulation and may be precursors to insulation failure. Thus many efforts have been made to utilize the PD patterns to predict insulation conditions. In the late 1980s, Richard Van Brunt noted that progress in the development of reliable methods for PD pattern recognition was being hampered by a failure to understand the physical mechanisms that governed the stochastic properties of partial discharges.

In response to this need, NIST developed an electronic system for measuring conditional amplitude, phase, and time probability distributions of pulsating phenomena [13]. This system was designed to investigate the conditional characteristics (or memory effects) of PD phenomena occurring in DC or low frequency AC systems. The device was called the Stochastic Analyzer for Pulsating Phenomena (SAPP), and was awarded an R&D100 award in 1990.

Initially, the system was used to analyze PD behavior for a point-plane electrode geometry in rare gases. This work led to investigations of more complex gaseous dielectrics, such as those containing O₂ and SF₆. An example of this type of analysis is shown in Figure 3 where the unconditional pulse-amplitude distribution is shown to be comprised of many narrow conditional distributions related to the time between discharge pulses. Investigation of these types of systems provided a clear explanation of the physical

processes, such as space charge migration, that affect the generation of partial discharges in dielectric gases.

Eventually, even more complex systems consisting of gaseous and solid dielectrics were investigated to determine the effects of PD on solid insulators. This work provided evidence that stochastic analysis of PD could provide information related to the physical conditions existing near the PD site. A comprehensive review of PD research at NIST was presented in the CEIDP Whitehead Memorial Lecture in 1994 [14].

Greenhouse Implications and SF₆ Substitutes

Sulfur hexafluoride is a potent greenhouse gas with a very long atmospheric lifetime. This has raised public concern over the use of SF₆, even though the total contribution of atmospheric SF₆ to global warming is very small. In response to this concern, NIST worked with the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency and the electric equipment industry to perform an extensive review of potential replacement dielectrics for SF₆ [1].

While no gas was identified that combined the high dielectric strength of SF₆ with its other favorable properties, it was determined that dilute mixtures of SF₆ with N₂ could perform nearly as well in many applications while using significantly less SF₆ [1,15]. This concept has been subsequently adopted by many utilities and electrical equipment manufacturers, and new equipment designs are being developed to fully utilize SF₆-N₂ mixtures. Other potential SF₆ substitutes include high pressure N₂, SF₆-He mixtures, and CO₂, depending upon the application. Further research is required to fully determine the suitability of these gases for dielectric applications.

Conclusions

Gaseous dielectrics research has enjoyed a long and productive history at NIST. Much of the research performed at NIST and elsewhere in this field has enabled industry to develop complex gaseous dielectrics applications to the point where they are considered nearly routine.

However, new challenges continue to arise in gaseous dielectrics, including global warming issues, higher performance requirements, and improved diagnostic applications. NIST supports investigations in these areas by continued interactions with CEIDP, and by hosting of the last two International Symposia on Gaseous Dielectrics in 1998 [16] and 2001 [17]. NIST plans to continue to host future International Symposia on Gaseous Dielectrics with Gaseous Dielectrics X scheduled to take place in 2004.

Figure 3: Normalized conditional pulse-amplitude distributions for negative point-plane corona pulses for the indicated time separations between pulses. The unconditional distribution is shown for comparison [14].

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Author address: James K. Olthoff, National Institute of Standards and Technology, 100 Bureau Drive, Gaithersburg, MD, USA 20899-8110, Email: james.olthoff@nist.gov.